

EFFECT OF THE SIMULTANEOUS ACTION OF RADIATIONS OF DIFFERENT FREQUENCIES ON THE BROMINATION OF CINNAMIC ACID AND STILBENE.

BY J. C. GHOSH, S. K. BHATTACHARYYA AND M. L. NARASIMHA MURTHI.

The simultaneous action of radiations of different frequencies on photochemical reactions has already been studied in many cases and the results so far obtained may be classified into three groups:

(i) Reactions in which the simultaneous action of radiations of different frequencies produce an effect which is equal to the sum of the effects of the individual radiations, *e.g.*, the oxidation of quinine by chromic acid studied by Luther and Forbes (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 770) and the bromination of toluene by Bruner and Czarnecki (*Bull. Acad. Sci. Cracow*, 1910, 516).

(ii) In a fairly large number of cases it has been found, however, that the combined effect of two radiations is less than the sum of the individual effects. This has been encountered in the bromination of cinnamic acid in carbon tetrachloride, alcohol and benzene solutions, studied by Plotnikow (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1912, **79**, 641), in the photochemical oxidation of hydriodic acid by oxygen in aqueous solutions by Padoa and Miss Vita (*Gazzetta*, 1924, **54**, 147), and in the oxidation of oxalic acid by ferric chloride by the latter authors. They have also observed the diminished effect in the bromination of cinnamic acid in chloroform and carbon tetrachloride solutions (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, **21**, 573) and in the absorption of carbon dioxide by green plant (*Gazzetta*, 1928, **58**, 647). Recently Ghosh and Bhattacharyya (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, **B 31**, 420) have shown that in the oxidation of mandelic acid by bromine the combined effect of two radiations is less than the sum of the individual effects.

(iii) As examples of reaction, where the combined effect of two radiations is greater than that given by the additive rule, may be mentioned the photosynthesis of hydrochloric acid by Padoa (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1926, **120**, 202), the isomeric transformation of *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde to *o*-nitrosobenzoic acid by Weigert and Kunmerer (*Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 1207), and the photolysis of potassium ferric oxalate by Allmand and Webb (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1518), the decomposition of ammonia by Kuhn (*Compt. rend.*, 1923, **177**, 956) and the reactions between iodide and various salts of sodium and potassium, and between oxalic acid and chromic acid, potassium

permanganate, and between bromine and sodium potassium tartrate studied by Mukherjee and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 33, 850). But a quantitative explanation of the observed results has rarely been attempted. In the oxidation of mandelic acid by bromine, Ghosh and Bhattacharyya (*loc. cit.*) have established a definite relationship between the combined effect and the individual effects of two radiations of different frequencies.

The object of the present investigation is to find out whether any definite relationship exists between the combined effect and the individual effects of two radiations of different frequencies in the bromination of cinnamic acid and also stilbene. The kinetics of the bromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene in $546\mu\mu$ and $536\mu\mu$ were studied by Berthoud (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1925, 21, 554), and notably by Ghosh and Purkayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 261; 1927, 4, 409, 553). These photochemical reactions are peculiar in some respects. They are unimolecular with respect to bromine but there is a slight diminution in the value of the velocity constant with increase in time.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The source of radiation was a quartz mercury point-o-lite lamp, run at a constant current of 2.3 amperes and at a constant voltage of 35 volts. A parallel beam of light was obtained by placing a convex lens at its focal length from the lamp. The reaction cell (1.5 cm. \times 1.5 cm. \times 0.5 cm. in the case of cinnamic acid and 1.8 cm. \times 1.8 cm. \times 0.5 cm. in the case of stilbene) made of plane glass plates fused into one another with a stopper at the top, was placed inside a double jacketed metal box with two windows side by side, one for the passage of light of one frequency, and the other for light of a different frequency. The temperature was kept constant by passing, with the aid of a circulating pump, water from a thermostat through the annular space of the box. The light beam was passed through the glass cells C_1 and C_2 , each 2 cm. thick, containing a 2% solution of copper sulphate to cut off the heat rays and then through the filters F_1 and F_2 for making the light monochromatic. The following filters were used :

- (I) for $406\mu\mu$: mercury violet
- (II) for $436\mu\mu$: Zeiss monochromatic blue filter C
- (III) for $546\mu\mu$: Schott and Gen Green VGI.

For intensity variation "Nitra glass" filters were used.

The following arrangement was adopted for the simultaneous action of two radiations of different frequencies on the reaction mixture contained

in the reaction cell. A beam of light passing through the filters C_1 and F_1 was reflected by a plane glass mirror M_1 at an angle of 45° and then passed through the stoppered rectangular cell C . Similarly a beam of light of a different frequency passing initially through the filters C_2 and F_2 (through the other window of the metal box) was reflected on to the reaction cell by the mirror M_2 . The relative positions of the mirrors and the reaction cell are closely shown in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1.

C—Reaction cell; C_1, C_2 — CuSO_4 filters; F_1, F_2 —monochromatic filters;
S—quartz point-o-lite lamp; W—double jacketed metal box.

The intensity of the absorbed radiation was measured by means of a Moll thermopile and Moll galvanometer calibrated by means of a standard lamp supplied by the "Bureau of Standards". The intensity of the incident radiation was found by observing the deflections produced by the monochromatic radiation after passing through the solvent alone. The intensity of the absorbed radiation was calculated from the data of the molecular extinction coefficient of bromine found by Ghosh and Bhattacharyya (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1936, B 32, 145). ϵ (molecular extinction coefficient) as found by them is 26.5 for $546\mu\mu$, 131.1 for $436\mu\mu$, and 130.5 for $406\mu\mu$.

Merck's 'extra pure' cinnamic acid and Schuchardt's pure stilbene further purified by crystallisation were used. The bromine was also of Merck's extra pure "Reagent" variety. For making solutions Merck's extra pure CCl_4 further purified by distillation over fused CaCl_2 was used.

The velocity of reaction was determined by pipetting out 0.27 c.c. of the reaction mixture and titrating iodometrically with 0.01M-thiosulphate by means of a microburette. The reactions were all carried out at 31° .

The compositions of the reaction mixtures used in this investigation

are identical with those used by Ghosh and Purkayastha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 409).

All the experiments in this investigation were finished within one hour of the exposure. During this period there is no dark reaction between bromine and cinnamic acid or stilbene.

The Light Reactions.

The kinetics of the reactions were studied in three monochromatic radiations 546, 436 and 406 $\mu\mu$ individually and under the simultaneous action of two radiations, violet (406 $\mu\mu$) and blue (436 $\mu\mu$), violet (406 $\mu\mu$) and green (546 $\mu\mu$), and blue (436 $\mu\mu$) and green (546 $\mu\mu$). The velocity constants are all calculated as unimolecular constants.

$$k = \frac{2.3}{t} \log_{10} \frac{a}{a-x}$$

The experimental results are tabulated in Tables I and II. The significance of each column will be found from the discussion. In the tables below, I is the light energy absorbed per sq. cm. per second by the bromine molecules. K is the unimolecular velocity constant.

$$V_i = 406\mu\mu, B_i = 436\mu\mu, G_i = 546\mu\mu, E = Nh\nu.$$

From the Tables I and II it will be found that

(a) The combined effect of two radiations is always less than the sum of the two individual effects.

(b) The velocity constant in pure monochromatic radiation varies as the square root of the intensity of absorbed radiation.

DISCUSSION.

In the photobromination of cinnamic acid and stilbene in CCl_4 solution, the velocity of reaction for single monochromatic radiation (λ_1) can be deduced from the following equations postulated by Ghosh (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, **B9**, 155).

In these reactions the concentration of Br_{λ_1} atom per c.c. in the stationary state is given by

$$\text{Br}_{\lambda_1} = \frac{I}{\sqrt{K_1}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{I_{\lambda_1}}{E_{\lambda_1}}}$$

Hence
$$-\frac{I}{[\text{Br}_2]} \cdot \frac{d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} = \frac{K_4 A}{K_3 + K_4 A} \cdot K_2 \cdot \frac{I}{\sqrt{K_1}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{I_{\lambda_1}}{E_{\lambda_1}}} = K_{\lambda_1} \text{ (observed).}$$

We assume that every collision between two Br atoms leads to the formation of a molecule of bromine in presence of an inert solvent molecule, and hence K_1 is independent of the nature of the radiation which causes photo-dissociation of the molecules of bromine into atoms; but that velocity constants K_2, K_3, K_4 , which are subsequent dark processes, depend on the energy content of the bromine atoms which initiate the reaction chain.

We shall use the symbols,

$$\text{Br}_{\lambda_1} = \frac{K_4 A}{K_3 + K_4 A} \cdot K_2 \text{ for } \lambda_1 ;$$

$$\frac{I_{\lambda_1}}{E_{\lambda_1}} = V_1, \quad \text{Br}_{\lambda_1} = n_1$$

or
$$\text{Br}_{\lambda_1} = K_{\lambda_1} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{I}{K_1}} \cdot \frac{I}{\sqrt{V_1}}$$

For simultaneous action of two radiations λ_1 and λ_2 ,

$$\begin{aligned} n_1 + n_2 &= \text{Br}_{\lambda_1} + \text{Br}_{\lambda_2} \\ &= \frac{I}{\sqrt{K_1}} \left[\frac{I_{\lambda_1}}{E_{\lambda_1}} + \frac{I_{\lambda_2}}{E_{\lambda_2}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &= \frac{I}{\sqrt{K_1}} \cdot [V_1 + V_2]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \text{ (a)} \end{aligned}$$

Again,

$$\text{Rate of formation of } \text{Br}_{\lambda_1} = \frac{I_{\lambda_1}}{E_{\lambda_1}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Rate of disappearance of } \text{Br}_{\lambda_1} &= K_1 [\text{Br}_{\lambda_1}^2 + \text{Br}_{\lambda_1} \cdot \text{Br}_{\lambda_2}] \\ &= K_1 [n_1^2 + n_1 \cdot n_2] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{That is, } V_1 = K_1 [n_1^2 + n_1 \cdot n_2]$$

$$\text{Similarly, } V_2 = K_1 [n_2^2 + n_1 \cdot n_2]$$

Solving for $\frac{n_1}{n_2}$, we get,

$$\frac{n_1}{n_2} = \frac{I}{2} \left\{ - \left(\frac{V_2 - V_1}{V_2} \right) \pm \sqrt{\left(\frac{V_2 - V_1}{V_2} \right)^2 + 4 \cdot \frac{V_1}{V_2}} \right\} \quad \dots (\beta)$$

Hence n_1 and n_2 are known from equations (a) and (b) taking the positive values.

The velocity constant due to the simultaneous action of two radiations λ_1 and λ_2 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} - \frac{I}{[\text{Br}_2]} \cdot \frac{d[\text{Br}_2]}{dt} &= K_{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2} = \text{Br}_{\lambda_1} n_1 + \text{Br}_{\lambda_2} n_2 \\ &= K_{\lambda_1} \cdot \sqrt{K_1} \cdot \frac{I}{\sqrt{V_1}} \cdot n_1 + K_{\lambda_2} \sqrt{K_1} \cdot \frac{I}{\sqrt{V_2}} \cdot n_2 \end{aligned}$$

where K_{λ_1} = observed velocity constant under the influence of monochromatic radiation λ_1 ,

K_{λ_2} = observed velocity constant under the influence of radiation λ_2 .

In the columns X and XI of Tables I and II are given the calculated and experimentally found velocity constants. They agree very well within the limits of experimental error and this justifies the mechanism of reaction which has been developed above.

TABLE I

Cinnamic Acid.

Conc. of cinnamic acid = 0.024M.

" " bromine = 0.0204M.

I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	
$I_1 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{I_1}{E_{\lambda_1}}}$	$K_{\lambda_1} \times 10^4$	$K_{\lambda_1} \times 10^4$	$\frac{K_{\lambda_1}}{\sqrt{I_1/E_{\lambda_1}}}$	$I_2 \cdot \sqrt{\frac{I_2}{E_{\lambda_2}}}$	$K_{\lambda_2} \times 10^4$	$\frac{K_{\lambda_2}}{\sqrt{I_2/E_{\lambda_2}}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{I_1 + I_2}{E_{\lambda_1} E_{\lambda_2}}}$	$K_3 \times 10^4 = K_{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2} \times 10^4$	Calc.	Found.	
			(BI)	(Gr)				(BI + Gr.)			
(a)	94.9	5.868	2.23	38.00	132.9	7.788	2.02	25.94	9.746	2.96	3.16
(b)	94.9	5.868	2.23	38.00	46.9	4.62	1.29	27.93	7.467	2.55	2.65
(c)	94.9	5.868	2.23	38.00	24.4	3.333	0.87	26.10	6.748	2.37	2.23
(d)	32.3	3.423	1.06	30.96	132.9	7.788	2.02	25.94	8.597	2.28	2.44
(e)	32.3	3.423	1.06	30.96	24.4	3.333	0.87	26.10	4.777	1.37	1.71
(f)	16.2	2.42	0.88	36.37	132.9	7.788	2.02	25.94	8.149	2.19	2.18
(g)	16.2	2.42	0.88	36.37	46.9	4.62	1.20	27.93	5.217	1.55	1.54
(h)	50.2	4.267	1.59	37.27	240	10.47	2.745	26.22	11.3	2.92	3.33
(i)	50.2	4.267	1.59	37.27	80	6.033	1.637	27.13	7.39	2.11	2.40
(j)	50.2	4.267	1.59	37.27	40	4.266	1.127	26.41	6.033	1.92	2.23
(k)	16.7	2.463	0.93	37.77	240	10.47	2.745	26.22	10.52	2.82	3.13
(l)	8.4	1.744	0.575	32.98	240	10.47	2.745	26.22	10.6	2.87	2.78

TABLE I (contd.).

	(Gr)		(VI)		(Gr + VI)						
(a)	240	10.47	2.745	26.22	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	12.13	3.02	3.15
(b)	80	6.033	1.637	27.13	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	7.136	2.08	2.23
(c)	40	4.266	1.127	26.41	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	5.719	1.70	1.92
(d)	240	10.47	2.745	26.22	14.2	2.198	0.72	32.75	10.68	2.96	2.83
(e)	40	4.266	1.127	26.41	14.2	2.198	0.72	32.75	4.799	1.33	1.70
(f)	132.9	7.788	2.01	25.81	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	8.66	2.38	2.67
(g)	50.9	4.297	1.40	32.58	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	5.741	1.91	2.05
(h)	25.5	3.087	0.94	30.45	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	4.906	1.68	1.71
(i)	132.9	7.788	2.01	25.81	14.2	2.198	0.72	32.75	8.091	2.13	2.35
(j)	25.5	3.087	0.98	30.45	14.2	2.198	0.72	32.75	3.796	1.19	1.31

	(VI)		(BI)		(VI + BI)						
(a)	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	114	6.363	2.40	37.71	7.473	2.75	2.36
(b)	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	38	3.713	1.48	39.87	5.318	1.96	1.85
(c)	42.5	3.807	1.3	34.14	19	2.625	1.1	41.91	4.625	1.69	1.47
(d)	14.2	2.198	0.72	32.75	114	6.363	2.40	37.71	6.795	2.53	2.19
(e)	14.2	2.198	0.72	32.75	19	2.625	1.1	41.91	3.424	1.31	1.08

TABLE II

Stilbene.

Conc. of stilbene = 0.024M. Conc. of bromine = 0.0216M.

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI
I_1	$\sqrt{\frac{I_1}{E_{\lambda_1}} \times 10^6}$	$K_{\lambda_1} \times 10^4$	$\frac{K_{\lambda_1}}{\sqrt{I_1/E_{\lambda_1}}}$	I_2	$\sqrt{\frac{I_2}{E_{\lambda_2}} \times 10^6}$	$K_{\lambda_2} \times 10^4$	$\frac{K_{\lambda_2}}{\sqrt{I_2/E_{\lambda_2}}}$	$\sqrt{\frac{I_1}{E_{\lambda_1}} + \frac{I_2}{E_{\lambda_2}}}$	$K_3 \times 10^4 = K_{\lambda_1} + \lambda_2$	Calc.	Found.
	(Gr)			(Bl)			(Gr + Bl)				
(a)	54.8	5.43	2.455	45.22	94	5.841	3.187	54.56	7.977	4.01	3.96
(b)	64.8	5.43	2.455	45.22	31.4	3.372	1.97	58.42	6.39	3.12	2.99
(c)	64.8	5.43	2.455	45.22	15.7	2.384	1.307	54.81	5.93	2.77	2.76
(d)	11.6	3.135	1.39	44.34	94	5.841	3.187	54.56	6.63	3.466	3.24
(e)	21.6	3.135	1.39	44.34	15.7	2.384	1.307	54.81	3.941	1.90	1.87
(f)	10.8	2.217	1.003	45.23	94	5.841	3.187	54.56	6.247	3.34	3.23
(g)	10.8	2.217	1.003	45.23	31.4	3.372	1.97	58.42	4.049	2.22	2.10

TABLE II (contd.).

ω	(a)	(B1)		(V1)		(B1 + V1)						
		94	5'841	3'187	54'56	64'7	4'708	1'65	35'05	7'501	3'52	3'47
	(b)	31'4	3'372	1'97	58'42	64'7	4'708	1'65	35'05	5'79	2'49	2'7
	(c)	15'7	2'384	1'307	54'81	64'7	4'708	1'65	35'05	5'277	2'66	1'75
	(d)	94	5'841	3'187	54'56	21'6	2'716	1'05	38'67	6'44	3'33	3'14
	(e)	15'7	2'384	1'307	54'81	21'6	2'716	1'05	38'67	3'615	1'65	1'56
		94	5'841	3'187	54'56	11'0	1'921	0'80	41'65	6'149	3'278	3'08
		31'4	3'372	1'97	58'42	11'0	1'921	0'80	41'65	3'881	2'00	1'86
		(V1)		(Gr)		(V1 + Gr)						
		64'7	4'708	1'66	35'05	64'8	5'43	2'455	45'22	7'186	2'94	3'22
		64'7	4'708	1'66	35'05	21'6	3'135	1'39	44'34	5'656	2'14	2'16
		64'7	4'708	1'66	35'05	10'8	2'217	1'003	45'23	5'204	1'92	1'94
		21'6	2'716	1'06	38'67	64'8	5'43	2'455	45'22	6'071	2'66	2'77
		21'6	2'716	1'06	38'67	10'8	2'217	1'003	45'23	3'595	1'45	1'30
		11'0	1'921	0'80	41'65	64'8	5'43	2'455	45'22	5'759	2'58	2'70
		11'0	1'921	0'80	41'65	21'6	3'135	1'39	44'34	3'676	1'61	1'46

Application of Einstein's Law of Photochemical Equivalence.

The calculation of the quantum efficiency has not much theoretical significance in these reactions; because the quantum efficiency has got a very high value and also the temperature coefficient is very large. These points have been discussed by Ghosh and Purkayastha (*loc. cit.*). The quantum efficiency has been calculated here only to have some idea of the mechanism of the reactions. In Table III the quantum efficiency in different wave-lengths has been tabulated.

A typical calculation is given below:—

$$\text{Wave-length} = 436\mu.$$

With 0.024M-cinnamic acid and 0.0206M-Br₂, the change in concentration of Br₂ in 25 minutes was 0.00655M. The reaction cell is 0.5 cm. thick and 1.5 × 1.5 sq. cm. in area. The energy absorbed per sq. cm. per sec. = 114 ergs. Total number of quanta of blue light absorbed per sec.

$$= \frac{114 \times 436 \times 10^{-7} \times 1.5 \times 1.5}{6.5 \times 10^{-27} \times 3 \times 10^{10}} = 7.46 \times 10^{13}.$$

Total number of molecules transformed per second

$$= \frac{0.5 \times 1.5 \times 1.5 \times 0.00655 \times 6.06 \times 10^{23}}{1000 \times 25 \times 60} = 297.7 \times 10^{13}$$

$$\therefore \gamma (\text{quantum efficiency}) = \frac{297.7 \times 10^{13}}{7.46 \times 10^{13}} = 40.$$

In the following table the compositions of the reaction mixtures are similar to those used in Tables I and II. *I* is the intensity of radiation absorbed by bromine in ergs per sq. cm. per second, γ is the quantum efficiency.

TABLE III.

λ .	Cinnamic acid.		Stilbene.	
	<i>I</i> .	γ .	<i>I</i> .	γ .
406 μ	42.5	72	64.7	61.2
	14.2	127	21.6	125
			10.8	208
436 μ	114	40	94	71
	50.2	63.5	31.4	144
	32.3	84.8	15.7	214
	16.2	132.5		
546 μ	240	15.6	64.8	48.7
	132	24.8	21.6	135
	80	32.6	10.8	176
	24.4	68.6		